

A True Value For the Golden Ratio: $\varphi = \frac{a+2a}{|a|}$

Take any whole number and apply it in the formula and you end up with the output of 3. Doesn't matter if the number is a positive or a negative. Take any matrix (I've tried it up to 25 inputs) and apply the formula as a vector algorithm and you get this very interesting 0-3 identity matrix. Most interesting are the -0' and the true 0's. The algorithm renders chaos to calm.

Array Creation Functions
Instructions are in the task pane to the left. Complete and submit each task one at a time.

Task 1

```
1 x = rand(5)
2 plot(x)
3
```

Task 2

```
4 y = (x+(2*x))/abs(x)
5 plot(y)
6
```

Task 3

```
7
8
```

Further Practice

```
9
10
```

x = 5x5

0.2760	0.4984	0.7513	0.9593	0.8407
0.6797	0.9597	0.2551	0.5472	0.2543
0.6551	0.3404	0.5060	0.1386	0.8143
0.1626	0.5853	0.6991	0.1493	0.2435
0.1190	0.2238	0.8909	0.2575	0.9293

y = 5x5

3.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000
0.0000	3.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000
-0.0000	0.0000	3.0000	-0.0000	0.0000
0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	3.0000	-0.0000
-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	3.0000

HOME LIVE EDITOR VIEW

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createarrays.mlx

Array Creation Functions

Instructions are in the task pane to the left. Complete and submit each task one at a time.

Task 1

```
1 x = rand(25);
2 plot(x);
3
```

Task 2

```
4 y = (x+(2*x))/abs(x);
5 plot(y);
6
```

Task 3

7

8

Further Practice

9

10

x - 25x25

0.3580	0.1622	0.8687	0.4173	0.1690	0.6443	0.9797	0.9631	0.9037	...
0.1966	0.7943	0.0844	0.0497	0.6491	0.3786	0.4389	0.5468	0.8909	
0.2511	0.3112	0.3998	0.9027	0.7317	0.8116	0.1111	0.5211	0.3342	
0.6160	0.5285	0.2599	0.9448	0.6477	0.5328	0.2581	0.2316	0.6987	
0.4733	0.1656	0.8001	0.4909	0.4509	0.3507	0.4087	0.4889	0.1978	
0.3517	0.6020	0.4314	0.4893	0.5470	0.9390	0.5949	0.6241	0.0305	
0.8308	0.2630	0.9106	0.3377	0.2963	0.8759	0.2622	0.6791	0.7441	
0.5853	0.6541	0.1818	0.9001	0.7447	0.5502	0.6028	0.3955	0.5000	
0.5497	0.6892	0.2638	0.3692	0.1890	0.6225	0.7112	0.3674	0.4799	
0.9172	0.7482	0.1455	0.1112	0.6868	0.5870	0.2217	0.9880	0.9047	

y - 25x25

3.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	...
0.0000	3.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	
0.0000	-0.0000	3.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	
0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	3.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	
-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	3.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	
0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	3.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	
-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	3.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	
0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	3.0000	
0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	3.0000	
-0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000	-0.0000	

The first plot shows a 25x1 vector of random noise. The second plot shows a 25x1 vector of values that are mostly zero but have sharp peaks reaching up to 3.0. This is the result of the formula y = (x+(2*x))/abs(x).

This beautiful formula is the explanation for how all unfolds from the One.

